

CA20104 – Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age (PhysAgeNet)

Deliverable D1.3

*D1.3- Description tool for PA and exercise interventions, based on
EBM standards*

Contributors

Working Group 1

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1. INTRODUCTION

Exercise interventions for older adults have been shown to deliver a broad spectrum of benefits: improved mobility and reduced falls (He et al. 2025), enhanced well-being and quality of life (Bragina et al. 2018), better cognitive function and mental health (Akalp et al. 2024), and a lower risk of chronic diseases (Wang et al. 2024) as well as depression (Zhang et al. 2025). These outcomes contribute to functional independence and healthy aging, and they justify the growing use of structured exercise in both clinical and community settings.

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses are core components of evidence-based medicine (EBM). They synthesize and critically appraise large and heterogeneous bodies of research, which enables clinicians, policy makers, and allied health professionals to integrate the best available evidence into decisions about patient care and public health programming. By consolidating results across trials, these methods increase statistical power, clarify the magnitude and consistency of effects, and identify important gaps that warrant future investigation.

To conduct such evidence syntheses rigorously, authors of primary studies must report exercise interventions with sufficient detail and clarity. Comprehensive reporting is essential for reproducibility, for efficient identification and comparison of studies during systematic reviews and meta-analyses, and for designing evidence-based, tailored programs for older adults (Wollesen et al. 2024). Complete descriptions of intervention content and delivery improve transparency, which allows readers to evaluate methodological quality and judge the likelihood and sources of bias (Blanco et al. 2024). High-quality reporting also assists researchers in mapping where the evidence is sparse, prioritizing research questions, and designing trials that address known limitations.

Existing reporting guidelines provide helpful structure, yet few are explicitly tailored to exercise interventions in older adults. There is a clear need to adapt and update current frameworks so they are directly applicable to aging populations, whose comorbidities, functional limitations, and safety considerations differ from those of younger adults. Such guidance should specify core elements that enable replication and synthesis: the FITT principles (frequency, intensity, time, and type), progression rules, supervision and provider qualifications, setting and equipment, adherence and fidelity measures, safety monitoring and adverse event definitions, comparator descriptions, and any strategies for individualization or risk stratification.

Exercise trials present distinctive challenges because interventions are complex, often multimodal, and typically personalized to baseline capacity and clinical status. A review of systematic reviews assessing the reporting quality of physical exercise interventions across health conditions found that, compared with drug trials, exercise trials frequently exhibit lower methodological quality, a higher risk of bias, and less consistent reporting of adverse events (Hansford et al. 2022; Hansford et al. 2024). These shortcomings reduce confidence in pooled estimates, hinder dose–response analyses, and make it harder to translate findings into pragmatic guidance.

In summary, although reporting standards for randomized controlled trials exist and the benefits of exercise for older adults are well documented, the lack of standardized, population-specific reporting of exercise components limits generalizability and constrains the development of tailored, evidence-based programs. Establishing clear and consistent reporting requirements, including FITT parameters and key training characteristics, would help researchers and practitioners identify actionable recommendations, replicate and scale effective protocols, and build a stronger foundation for physical activity guidance in later life.

2. AIM OF THE DESCRIPTION TOOL

The purpose for developing this description tool for physical activity and exercise interventions, grounded in evidence-based medicine (EBM) principles, was to produce clear and standardized guidelines—while also considering already established recommendations—for randomized controlled trials. By incorporating the unique characteristics of exercise interventions in older adults, we introduce an expanded reporting framework aimed at enhancing the transparency, methodological rigor, and completeness of exercise intervention descriptions. This approach is intended to ensure that the documented benefits for the older population can be accurately interpreted, reliably replicated, and effectively translated into clinical and real-world practice.

3. DESCRIPTION TOOL

PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science were searched for guidelines on reporting physical exercise, with no limits on publication date. Records were screened using the following inclusion criteria:

Study type: reporting guidelines for randomized controlled trials, for example CONSORT (Schulz et al. 2010).

Intervention focus: guidance capturing exercise specific variables such as FITT, for example CERT (Schulz et al. 2010).

Reproducibility: guidance providing sufficient procedural detail to enable intervention replication.

Target population: applicability to human studies, including older adults.

Outcome reporting: guidance facilitating clear and comprehensive outcome reporting.

From the retrieved materials, CONSORT (Schulz et al. 2010) was selected as the primary framework for refinement. Items were integrated based on findings from Stages 1 and 2. A preliminary list was compiled from the Stage 1 Delphi results, gaps identified in the Stage 2 literature review, and expert input from the core working group with experience in exercise trials in older adults.

The introduction was structured to align the study hypothesis with the primary outcomes and to state the theoretical models informing the intervention design. Participant descriptors included age, education, physical activity level, and technology familiarity when applicable. Intervention reporting was organized according to the FITT principle, with emphasis on intensity and adherence assessment, and included potential harms and dropout considerations, particularly for technology supported delivery.

The extended checklist was discussed during a hybrid meeting with PhysAgeNet COST Action experts (N = 28), covering three issues: item relevance and completeness, placement within CONSORT sections, and integration of digital technology aspects. Wording was revised as needed for clarity.

The checklist was then converted into an online LimeSurvey questionnaire comprising 108 items. Respondents rated each item's relevance on a 0 – 10 Likert scale and could provide free text feedback. The survey was emailed to all PhysAgeNet members (N = 442) with a two week window from August 14 – 30, 2024. Informed consent was required.

Survey results were reviewed at a face-to-face meeting with Working Group 1. Revisions were made by consensus using quantitative ratings and qualitative comments, and language clarity, grammar, and redundancy were addressed. The process yielded a focused set of reporting items covering participant characteristics, intervention components, adherence and compliance, outcomes, and digital delivery features.

The final consensus step consisted of an online survey of journal editors who frequently publish exercise studies involving older adults. Editors rated 208 items on a 0 – 10 Likert scale and provided qualitative comments. Items from the original CONSORT checklist that were unchanged were omitted. A total of 311 editors were identified through online searches and contacted by email; 19 responded, 6 participated, and 13 declined, citing lack of relevant expertise (n = 9), unavailability (n = 2), or no longer serving as editor in chief (n = 1). All participating editors provided informed consent at the start of the online questionnaire.

Cf. Wollesen et al., 2024 (<https://zenodo.org/communities/egrapa/records>)

Table 1: Items of the Description Tool along with the Expert and editor ratings on the integrated items of the tool.

Items	Expert Rating (M±SD)	Editor Rating (M±SD)
Title and abstract		
1a) Identify as an RCT in the title; if possible, follow the PICO scheme	8.64 ± 1.8	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
1b) Include a structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstract)	8.96 ± 1.6	9.16 ± 1.4
1b1) Describe the population (healthy, diseased, etc.)	9.54 ± 1.2	9.31 ± 1.2
1b2) If the title cannot integrate the PICO scheme (Population-Intervention-Comparison-Outcome) according to a word limit, report all PICO criteria in the abstract	8.32 ± 2.1	8.23 ± 2.1
1c) Report age (mean >60 years; age range)	9.11 ± 1.6	8.94 ± 1.6
1d) Report number of males/females	8.36 ± 1.9	9.00 ± 1.7
1e) Report information about the FITT principle	8.07 ± 2.3	7.94 ± 2.4
Introduction		
Background and objectives		
2a) Describe scientific background and give rationale	9.08 ± 1.5	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
2a1) Describe potential theoretical models or mechanisms (including summary of previous studies) explaining why the proposed intervention might work and how they are related to the outcome of interest (e.g. cardiovascular adaptations or increase of muscle mass, etc.)	8.96 ± 1.2	9.03 ± 1.2
2b) Include specific objectives or hypotheses	8.92 ± 1.7	9.68 ± 0.6
2b1) Formulate the research question and hypothesis according to the outcomes of interest	9.26 ± 1.0	9.17 ± 1.6
2b2) Justify if the outcomes match the research questions	8.22 ± 1.3	8.61 ± 1.8

Methods		
Trial design		
3a) Describe trial design (such as parallel, cluster, factorial) including allocation ratio	9.55 ± 0.7	9.55 ± 1.4
3b) Describe changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	9.55 ± 0.7	9.32 ± 1.4
Participants		
4a) Report eligibility criteria for participants, including:	10.00 ± 0.0	9.35 ± 1.8
4a1) Mean age or median of sample age depending on the distribution of your sample, and age range	9.50 ± 1.3	
4a2) Inclusion/exclusion criteria	9.50 ± 2.0	9.74 ± 0.8
4b) Provide a table comparing the main characteristics of the different groups of participants, including:	8.11 ± 3.0	9.00 ± 2.1
4b1) "PA level at baseline" and end of intervention; change to "PA level/functional capacity at baseline"	7.95 ± 2.8	
4b2) Percentage of women in each group	8.90 ± 2.0	
4b3) Mean level of education (and SD) of the participants in each group, specify if years or degree; clarify but leave to author which to choose	7.85 ± 2.3	6.67 ± 2.7
4b4) Health status (objective and/or subjective health?)	9.11 ± 1.5	8.48 ± 2.2
4b5) If the study design includes technology support or usage, include: Experience with technology	8.75 ± 2.2	8.41 ± 1.4
4b6) Participants' access to the technology	8.10 ± 2.5	8.43 ± 1.3
4b7) Digital literacy	8.37 ± 2.4	7.80 ± 1.9
4b8) Aspects of tailoring the technology	7.90 ± 2.8	8.03 ± 2.0
4c) Describe settings and locations where the data was collected	8.65 ± 2.0	8.87 ± 1.5
Interventions		
5) Describe the interventions for each group with sufficient details. If multimodal, provide details for every modality to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered., including a description of:	9.67 ± 0.7	9.61 ± 0.7
5a1) Exercise type (single mode or multimodal)	9.85 ± 0.4	9.45 ± 1.1
5a2) Exercise frequency (number of sessions per week)	9.90 ± 0.3	9.65 ± 0.7

5a3) Duration of exercise (length of time spent on each exercise session in the intervention (in minutes))	9.80 ± 0.4	9.77 ± 0.5
5a4) Exercise intensity (level of difficulty or effort exerted during the exercise in the intervention and methods used to assess and monitor it, e.g., integrate the percentage of HR max/HR reserve/VO ₂ max/VO ₂ peak; RPE/ fatigue before and after intervention/report also the scale (i.e., 6-20, 1-10))	9.80 ± 0.4	9.35 ± 1.2
5b) Describe exercise physiology aspects (cardiovascular, metabolic, and muscular adaptations), Including a description of:	8.56 ± 2.3	9.47 ± 0.7
5b1) Exercise progression (increase in the difficulty, duration, and frequency of the exercise program)	9.60 ± 0.8	
5b2) Intensity changes in different exercise types	9.00 ± 2.2	9.39 ± 0.9
5b3) Resting times (duration of rest or recovery between sets or exercises during the intervention)	9.40 ± 1.3	9.23 ± 1.0
5b4) METs for exercise program/its components: This refers to the estimated energy expenditure during physical activity intervention	8.05 ± 2.3	8.00 ± 1.8
5b5) If technology was used, describe if and how exposure is controlled in the technology	9.16 ± 1.2	8.57 ± 1.7
5c) Describe whether there is any non-exercise component	8.10 ± 2.4	9.30 ± 1.2
5e) Describe exercise settings, including a description of:	9.41 ± 0.9	8.97 ± 1.5
5e1) Whether exercise is performed individually or in a group	9.70 ± 0.7	
5e2) Whether exercise is supervised or unsupervised and how exercise was monitored	9.65 ± 0.9	9.45 ± 0.8
5e3) Any home program component	9.05 ± 2.1	9.16 ± 1.3
5e4) If technology is used, describe how exercise was monitored (e.g., telemonitoring)	8.90 ± 2.2	9.37 ± 0.9
5e5) Whether the exercises are tailored or generic (one-size fits all): If tailored, describe how it was tailored to the individual	9.30 ± 0.9	9.73 ± 0.6
5e6) Whether there are any simultaneous, consecutive exercise/ intervention components (add a short-detailed description)	8.37 ± 2.1	9.52 ± 0.9
5e7) Type of exercise equipment	9.30 ± 1.0	9.10 ± 1.5
5e8) If technology is used describe: The design, specific functions (including a list of examples with description), software, interface, adaptation methods, algorithms	8.95 ± 1.8	8.57 ± 1.5
5e9) If technology is used describe: How progression is programmed	8.80 ± 1.8	8.70 ± 1.4

5e10) If technology is used describe: How the outcome is calculated if available	8.90 ± 2.0	9.13 ± 1.3
5e11) If technology is used describe: Specific match between technology of intervention and outcome	8.90 ± 1.8	8.67 ± 1.6
5f) Describe type of control group in detail (e.g., was the control group active or passive? If active, what type of activity did they perform?)	9.58 ± 1.0	9.42 ± 1.1
5f1) Report whether the control group was blinded	8.79 ± 2.4	9.48 ± 1.0
5f2) Describe if and how exposure is controlled for the control group in the Technology	8.74 ± 2.1	9.27 ± 1.2
5g) Describe motivational control aspects	8.11 ± 2.2	9.16 ± 1.5
5g1) Describe how compliance/adherence to exercise is measured/assessed	9.53 ± 0.7	
5g2) Describe of motivational strategies and behavioral change techniques if used	8.63 ± 2.2	9.13 ± 1.4
5g3) If applicable, how do participants get compensated for study participation	7.95 ± 2.3	8.61 ± 1.7
5h) Describe the extent to which the intervention was not delivered as planned if applicable	8.63 ± 2.1	9.26 ± 1.3
5i) Control for confounding factors	8.74 ± 2.1	7.79 ± 2.0
5i1) If applicable, report beliefs and stereotypes of participants concerning the effects of regular exercise on health	7.55 ± 2.9	
5i2) Physical activity (PA) practiced by the participants beside the intervention. The method to measure PA level should be mentioned (e.g., actimeter, questionnaire)	8.60 ± 2.2	8.73 ± 1.7
5i3) If applicable, report participants' preference of the different groups for a specific intervention (particularly when several interventions are implemented)	8.10 ± 2.3	8.07 ± 2.0
Outcomes		
6a) Describe the pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	9.80 ± 0.5	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
6b) Describe any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	9.60 ± 0.8	
Sample size		
7a) Describe how sample size was determined	9.55 ± 0.8	
7b) When applicable, explain any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	8.80 ± 1.4	

Randomization: Sequence generation		
8a) Describe method used to generate the random allocation sequence	9.35 ± 0.8	
8b) Describe type of randomization; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	9.35 ± 1.0	
8c) Describe use of a minimization process (e.g., randomization according to baseline physical and cognitive levels of the participants)	9.20 ± 1.1	
Allocation concealment mechanism		
9) Describe mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	9.00 ± 1.3	
Implementation		
10) Report who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	8.25 ± 2.5	
Masking		
11a) Describe if a masking or blinding was applied, and if yes, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (e.g., participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes), and how	9.20 ± 1.2	
11a1) Describe if there were any blinding changes	8.68 ± 1.6	
11b) Describe possible similarities of interventions	7.79 ± 2.9	
Statistical methods		
12a) Describe statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	10.00 ± 0.0	
12b) Describe methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	9.85 ± 0.4	
12c) Describe type of analysis used: intention-to-treat, complete-case, perprotocol	9.45 ± 0.9	9.43 ± 1.1
12c1.1) Describe if the intention-to-treat analysis was used, which imputation technique was carried out to replace missing data	9.05 ± 2.1	9.43 ± 1.0
12c1.2) Describe if per-protocol analysis, what protocol was not followed		9.00 ± 1.5

Results		
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)		
13a) Describe for each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	9.80 ± 0.5	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
13b) Describe for each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	9.45 ± 1.8	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
13c) Describe for each group, percentage of compliance/adherence to the intervention	9.21 ± 1.9	8.80 ± 2.2
13c1.1) Describe if adverse events like injuries occur, number, dropouts, and reasons for dropouts	9.25 ± 2.0	8.97 ± 2.1
13c1.2) If technology was used, report on adverse events like injuries, number and reasons for dropouts according to the technology		8.69 ± 2.2
Recruitment		
14a) Report the dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	9,20 ± 1,9	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
14b) Report why the trial ended or was stopped	8,89 ± 1,9	
Baseline data		
15a) Provide a table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group (cf. 6)	9.79 ± 0.4	9.7 ± 0.7
15a1) Report mean age or median and age range per group	9.21 ± 2.1	
15a2) Report the standard deviation for the mean age per group.		9.2 ± 1.6
Numbers analyzed		
16) Report for each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by originally assigned groups	9.50 ± 0.8	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
Outcomes and estimation		
17a) For each primary and secondary outcomes report results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	9.45 ± 1.1	
17b) For binary outcomes present both absolute and relative effect sizes (recommended)	9.53 ± 0.8	
Ancillary analyses		

18) Report results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre specified from exploratory	9.50 ± 0.8	
Harms		
19a) Describe all important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	9.60 ± 0.8	
19a1) Describe if adverse events like injuries occurred, number of dropouts, and reasons for dropouts	9.11 ± 2.1	9.17 ± 1.8
19a2) If technology was used, report on adverse events like injuries, number and reasons for dropouts according to the technology	9.10 ± 2.1	8.93 ± 1.9
Discussion		
Limitations		
20a) Describe trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias (e.g., heterogeneity of characteristics, differences in baseline characteristics, changes in blinding), imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	9.20 ± 1.6	Omitted— identical to CONSORT.
20b) Describe unexpected changes regarding the whole study protocol	9.10 ± 2.0	
20c) Describe whether and how the results answer the RQ	8.70 ± 2.3	
20d) Discuss imprecision, relevant analyses differences in changes in different groups	8.80 ± 2.2	
20e) Discuss if surrogate markers answer RQ	8.11 ± 2.4	
20f) All aspects of 5i)	8.25 ± 2.4	
Generalizability		
21) Report and discuss generalizability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	9.28 ± 0.9	
21a) Report and discuss effect sizes	8.40 ± 2.3	
Interpretation		
22) Provide an interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	8.80 ± 1.9	
22a) Discuss all possible confounders that might change the demonstration effect	8.20 ± 2.5	

Other information	
23) Registration: Include registration number and name of trial registry	9.70 ± 0.7
24) Protocol: If available add where the full trial protocol can be accessed	9.15 ± 1.6
25) Funding: Report sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders, support by training/software development companies	9.89 ± 0.5

“Omitted—identical to CONSORT”. Note that some items were not sent to editors because they remained unchanged from their CONSORT version. Mean ± SD

4. KEY REFERENCES USED FOR DEVELOPPING DESCRIPTION TOOL

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Schulz, K. F., Altman, D. G., Moher, D., & CONSORT Group. (2010). CONSORT 2010 statement: Updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials. *BMJ (Clinical Research Ed.)*, 340, c332